

REAL TIME LOGO RECOGNITION USING YOLO ON ANDROID

Primbetov Abbaz

University of Tashkent for Applied Sciences, Gavhar Str.
1, Tashkent 100149, Uzbekistan
abbaz0203@mail.ru

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13364888>

Abstract: Humans can easily detect and identify objects present in an image. The human visual system is fast and accurate and can perform complex tasks like identifying multiple objects and detect obstacles with little conscious thought. For a long time, humans have been trying to make computers understand what is on the images. With the availability of large amounts of data, faster Graphics Processing Unit (GPU)s, and better algorithms, we can now easily train computers to detect and classify multiple objects within an image with high accuracy. The goal of this paper is to implement an object detection model suitable in terms of size and speed to run on an Android device and detect logos in real-time. The proposed approach is based on YOLOv2 (You Only Look Once) state-of-the-art, real-time object detection for logos and this project used the FlickrLogos-32 dataset. The experimental results show that we obtained a final accuracy of 82.3% and a speed of 35 fps (frames per second) on the NVidia GeForce GTX 1070.

Keywords: Object detection, Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), You Only Look Once (YOLO), Faster R-CNN (Region-based Convolutional Neural Networks).

INTRODUCTION

A logo is a graphical mark used to identify a company, organization, product or brand. Logos are used to represent a company's name, a particular product or service and are used heavily in the marketing of products and services [1-9]. Logos have become an integral part of a company's identity and a well-recognized logo can increase a company's goodwill. A logo usually has a recognizable and distinctive graphic design, stylized name or unique symbol for identifying an organization. It is affixed, included, or printed on all advertising, buildings, communications, literature, products, stationery, vehicles, etc. Logo can be seen anywhere in the surrounding in our daily life, such as in the streets, supermarkets, on the products or services, on administrative documents, etc. Examples of different logos are shown in Figure 1. Logo detection is a challenging object recognition and classification problem as there is no clear definition of what constitutes a logo. A logo can be thought of as an artistic expression of a brand, it can be either a (stylized) letter or text, a graphical figure or any combination of these [10]. Furthermore, some logos

Figure 1: Some figures illustrate that logos appear everywhere in our surrounding.

have a fixed set of colors with known fonts while others vary a lot in color and specialized unknown fonts [11-14]. Additionally, due to the nature of a logo (as brand identity), there is no guarantee about its context or placement in an image, in reality logos could appear on any product, background or advertising surface. Also, this problem has large intra-class variations e.g. for a specific brand, there exist various logos types (old and new Adidas logos, small and big versions of Nike) and inter-class variations e.g. there exists logos which belong to different brands but look similar (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: Logo variations exemplar images

android. Figure 3 shows the structure of Fast YOLO. The tiny version is composed of 9 convolution layers with leaky relu activations. Observe that after 6 maxpool the 446x446 input image becomes a 13x13xD image

Figure 3: The network of YOLOv2

YOLO divides up the image into a grid of 13 by 13 cells. In object detection, we also have to predict the location and the shape of an object, not only classification [29]. Therefore, the output of an object detection network becomes a little bit complicated. In our case of YOLOv2, the output is a 3-dimensional array (or Tensor in TensorFlow). Particularly in YOLOv2, the shape of output is 13x13xD, where D varies depending on how many classes of objects we want to detect (For example D=5 for a single class). The first 2-dimensional array (13x13) is called grid cells. So, there are 169 grid cells in total. One grid cell is 'responsible' for detecting 5 bounding boxes, that is we can detect up to 5 boxes on a grid cell. This means that the network can detect up to 169 x 5 = 845 boxes at once [30]. This number of bounding boxes a grid cell can detect is actually the number of Anchor-Boxes we prepare, and we can change this number to whatever we want. So, for example, if we want to detect humans and cars and think that just two Anchor-Boxes (vertical rectangle for humans, and horizontal rectangle for cars) are enough to detect them, then the number 5 above becomes 2. (In the paper of YOLOv2, this number is denoted as 'B'). Figure 4: shows the output of the network for YOLOv2 looks like this.

Layer	kernel	Stride/Filters	Output shape
Input			416x416x3
Convolution	3x3	1/16	416x416x16
MaxPooling	2x2	2	208x208x16
Convolution	3x3	1/32	208x208x32
MaxPooling	2x2	2	104x104x32
Convolution	3x3	1/64	104x104x64
MaxPooling	2x2	2	52x52x64
Convolution	3x3	1/128	52x52x128
MaxPooling	2x2	2	26x26x128
Convolution	3x3	1/256	26x26x256
MaxPooling	2x2	2	13x13x256
Convolution	3x3	1/512	13x13x512
MaxPooling	2x2	1	13x13x1024
Convolution	3x3	1/1024	13x13x1024
Convolution	3x3	1	13x13x1024
Convolution	1x1	1/175	13x13x175

Figure 4: The output of the network for YOLOv2
 Each grid cell has depth of D. The value of D depends on the number of classes we want to detect. When we have C classes of object, D is $D=B(5+C)$. The output of the network looks like this. There are $13 \times 13 = 169$ grid cells in total, and each grid cell can detect up to B bounding boxes. One bounding box has $5 + C$ properties, therefore a grid cell has $D = B \times (5+C)$ values

(this is depth) $\text{Tensor} = S \times S \times S \times (5+C)$ In our case classes number $C=30$ and $B=5$

Figure 5: This 13x13 tensor can be considered as a 13x13 grid representing the input image, where each cell of this tensor will hold the 5 box definitions and 30 class probabilities.

The input to the network is 416x416x3 image in YOLOv2-tiny. There is no fully connected layer in it [31]. (Table 1)

Table 1: Details of Network

Experimental Results

In our project we used FlickrLogos-32 dataset. The FlickrLogos-32 dataset contains photos showing brand logos and is meant for the valuation of multi-class logo recognition as well as logo retrieval methods on

real-world images. Logos of 32 different logo classes and 6000 negative images were collected by downloading them from Flickr. The dataset includes images, ground truth, annotations (bounding boxes plus binary masks), evaluation scripts and pre computed visual features [32]. The dataset FlickrLogos-32 contains photos depicting logos and is meant for the evaluation of multi-class logo detection/recognition as well as logo retrieval methods on real-world images. One of the most time-consuming and costly processes in constructing the Flickrlogos-32 database is to annotate logo objects from the collected product images. For each product image, a logo annotator needs to identify the logo objects, annotate the bounding box of each logo

object, and then tag it with the corresponding logo class id. Figure 5 shows examples of logo object annotation on product images.

Figure 5: Instruction example of logo object annotation. The left-hand side is rejected due to too loose bounding box.

Metric

mAP (mean Average Precision) is a popular metric in measuring the accuracy of object detectors like YOLO, SSD, etc. Average precision computes the average precision value for recall value over 0 to 1.

Using this criterium, we calculate the precision/recall curve. Then we compute a version of the measured precision/recall curve with precision monotonically,

Figure 6: Show us the result of mean average precision (mAP)

by setting the precision for recall r to the maximum precision obtained for any recall $r' > r$. Finally, we compute the AP as the area under this curve by numerical integration. No approximation is involved since the curve is piecewise constant and finally, we can calculate mean average precision object detection (mAP), resulting in a mAP value from 0 to 100% [33].

(Mean average precision) of 82% and it can track logos very smoothly. In mobile android phones (Honor 9) we have made the process result as shown in Figure 12 by conducting a series of experiments, the quantitative performance measure of logo detection. Training dark flow and our custom CNN architecture took an immense amount of time. We trained our models in batches of 64 in 8 mini-batches. This allowed us to efficiently train 64 images every step [34].

Training on a NVidia GeForce 1070, each step took 0.5 seconds. This allowed us to train each model for 2000 epochs, so we can observe the early stopping point and the weights that gave us the best accuracies. YOLO's implementation allowed us to save our weight files every 10000 steps, so we just let it continually train overnight so we can scrap the accuracy in the morning using a script. We have significant results that show our model works better with our dataset above with a little less than 2000 epochs. We trained up to 2000 epochs and the accuracy peaked at epoch 1500. We

experimented with running different learning rates our accuracy never got any better.

Figure 7. Shows the logo detection through Honor 9.

CONCLUSIONS

I have trained the model on the FlickrLogos-32 dataset and experiment results to show that YOLOv2 performs very well in real-time logo detection. By performing a comprehensive analysis of YOLOv2 over FlickrLogos-32 dataset, we found that the experiment result showed that we managed to achieve a final mean average precision (mAP) 82.53% and 30-35 FPS (frames per second) speed on an NVIDIA GeForce GTX 1070 and our models performed well at the detection, with very low false-positive rates possible for a fairly reasonably. The application runs smoothly on the current test hardware. However, the main part of the goal was successfully implemented, a working application that utilizes a neural network model for object detection..

REFERENCES

- [1] Feh'erv'ari, I., Appalaraju, S. (2019, January). Scalable logo recognition using proxies. In 2019 IEEE Winter Conference on Applications of Computer Vision (WACV) (pp. 715-725). IEEE.
- [2] Su, Hang, Xiatian Zhu, and Shaogang Gong. "Open logo detection challenge." arXiv preprint arXiv: 1807.01964 (2018).
- [3] Oliveira, G., Fraz'ao, X., Pimentel, A., Ribeiro, B. (2016, July). Automatic graphic logo detection via fast region-based convolutional networks. In 2016 International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN) (pp. 985-991). IEEE.
- [4] Hoi, S. C., Wu, X., Liu, H., Wu, Y., Wang, H., Xue, H., Wu, Q. (2015). Logo-net: Large-scale deep logo detection and brand recognition with deep region-based convolutional networks. arXiv preprint arXiv: 1511.02462.
- [5] Shafiee, M. J., Chywl, B., Li, F., Wong, A. (2017). Fast YOLO: A Fast You Only Look Once System for Real-time Embedded Object Detection in Video. arXiv: Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition.
- [6] Feh'erv'ari, Istv'an, and Srikar Appalaraju. "Scalable logo recognition using proxies." 2019 IEEE Winter

Conference on Applications of Computer Vision (WACV). IEEE, 2019.

[7] Ren, S., He, K., Girshick, R., Sun, J. (2015). Faster R-CNN: towards real-time object detection with region proposal networks. *Neural information processing systems*.

[8] S., He, K., Girshick, R., Sun, J. (2015). Faster r-cnn: Towards real-time object detection with region proposal networks. In *Advances in neural information processing systems* (pp. 91-99).

[9] Le, Viet Phuong. "Logo detection, recognition and spotting in context by matching local visual features." PhD diss., Universit'e de La Rochelle, 2015.

[10] [10] Eggert, C., Brehm, S., Winschel, A., Zecha, D. and Lienhart, R., 2017, July. A closer look: Small object detection in faster R-CNN. In *2017 IEEE international conference on multimedia and expo (ICME)* (pp. 421-426). IEEE.

[11] Saitov E.B., Akhmedov U.M. Tracking maximum power point of photovoltaic modules, *AIP Conference Proceedings*, 2023, 2789, 060005, <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0145470>

[12] Zikrillayev N., Ayupov K.a Mamarajabova Z.b, Yuldoshev I.a, Saitov E.a, Sabitova I.a Adaptation and optimization of a photovoltaic system for a country house, *E3S Web of Conferences*, 2023, 383, 04054, <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202338304054>

[13] Saitov, E., Kudenov, I., Qodirova, F., Askarov, D., Sultonova, M. Analysis of the performance and economic parameters of different types of solar panels taking into account degradation processes. *E3S Web of Conferences*, 2023, 383, 04059 <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202338304059>

[14] Saitov, E., Khushakov, G., Masharipova, U., Mamasaliyev, O., Rasulova, S. Investigation of the working condition of large power solar panel cleaning device. *E3S Web of Conferences*, 2023, 383, 04060, <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202338304060>

[15] Zikrillayev, N., Saitov, E., Toshov, J., Muradov, B., Muxtorov, D. Autonomous Solar Power Plant for Individual use Simulation in LTspice Software Package Booster Voltage Converter. *Proceedings of International Conference on Applied Innovation in IT*, 2023, 11(1), pp. 207–211, <https://doi:10.25673/101939>

[16] Yuldoshev, B., Saitov, E., Khaliyarov, J., Toshpulatov, S., Kholmurzayeva, F. Effect of Temperature on Electrical Parameters of Photovoltaic Module. *Proceedings of International Conference on Applied Innovation in IT*, 2023, 11(1), pp. 291–295, <https://doi:10.25673/101957>

[17] Saitov, E., Jurayev, O., Axrorova, S., Ismailov, J., Baymirzaev, B. Conversion and use of Solar Energy Calculation Methodology for Photovoltaic Systems, *Proceedings of International Conference on Applied Innovation in IT*, 2023, 11(1), pp. 227–232, <https://doi:10.25673/101942>

[18] Zikrillayev, N.F., Shoabdurahimova, M.M., Kamilov, T., Norkulov, N., Saitov, E.B. Obtaining manganese silicide films on a silicon substrate by the diffusion method.

Physical Sciences and Technology, 2022, 9(2), pp. 89–93, <https://doi.org/10.26577/phst.2022.v9.i2.011>

[19] Zikrillayev, N.F., Saitov, E.B., Ayupov, K.S., Yuldoshev, I.A. Determination of the resistance of external parameters to the degradation of the parameters of silicon photocells with input nickel atoms. *Physical Sciences and Technology*, 2022, 9(1), pp. 30–36, <https://doi.org/10.26577/phst.2022.v9.i1.04>

[20] Saitov, E.B., Kodirov, Sh., Beknazarova, Z.F., Nortoijiyev, A., Siddikov, N. Developing Renewable Sources of Energy in Uzbekistan Renewable Energy Short Overview: Programs and Prospects. *AIP Conference Proceedings*, 2022, 2432, 020015, <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0090438>

[21] E. B. Saitov; T. B. Sodiqov. Modeling an autonomous photovoltaic system in the MATLAB Simulink software environment, *AIP Conf. Proc.* 2432, 020022 (2022), <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0089914>

[22] E. B. Saitov, Sh. Kodirov, B. M. Kamanov, N. Imomkulov, I. Kudenov, Increasing the efficiency of autonomous solar photovoltaic installations for power supply of agricultural consumers, *AIP Conf. Proc.* 2432, 040036 (2022), <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0090439>

[23] F. Zikrillayev, E. B. Saitov, J. B. Toshov, B. K. Ilyasov, M. B. Zubaydullayev, A software package for determining the optimal composition and parameters of a combined autonomous power supply system based on renewable energy sources, *AIP Conf. Proc.* 2432, 020021 (2022), <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0090460>

[24] Zikrillayev Nurullo, Toshov Javohir, Saitov Elyor, Sodikov Temur, Development and selection of equipment for a peak autonomous photo power plant, *AIP Conf. Proc.* 2552, 030020 (2023) <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0117594>

[25] Turabdjanoj Sadritdin, Toshov Javohir, Saitov Elyor, Axmedov Usmonjon, Research of electrophysical parameters of different types of solar panels taking into account degradation processes, *AIP Conf. Proc.* 2552, 030019 (2023), <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0117592>

[26] Yu.M.Kurbonov, E.B.Saitov and B.M.Botirov, Analysis of the influence of temperature on the operating mode of a photovoltaic solar station, *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, Volume 614, 1st International Conference on Energetics, Civil and Agricultural Engineering 2020 14-16 October 2020, Tashkent, Uzbekistan, Citation 2020 IOP Conf. Ser.: Earth Environ. Sci. 614 012034, <https://doi:10.1088/1755-1315/614/1/012034>

[27] E.B. Saitov, Optimal model for additional operation of the storage system for photovoltaic wind power plants, *E3S Web of Conferences* 220, 01080 (2020), <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202022001080>

[28] E.B.Saitov, Y.B.Sobirov, I.A.Yuldoshev, I.R. Jurayev and Sh.Kodirov, Study of Solar Radiation and Wind Characteristics in Various Regions of Uzbekistan, *E3S Web of Conferences* 220, 01061 (2020), <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202022001061>

[29] E.B.Saitov, J.B.Toshov, A.O.Pulatov, B.M.Botirov and Yu.M.Kurbanov, Networked interactive solar panels over the roof photovoltaic system (PVS) and its cost analysis at Tashkent state technical University, *E3S Web of Conferences*

- 216, 01133 (2020),
<https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202021601133>
- [30] E.B. Saitov, Renewable energy development in Uzbekistan: current status, problems and solutions, E3S Web of Conferences 216, 01134 (2020),
<https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202021601134>
- [31] Sanjar Shoguchkarov, Isroil Yuldoshev, Elyor Saitov and Alisher Boliev, The effect of the surface geometry of a photovoltaic battery on its efficiency, E3S Web of Conferences 216, 01149 (2020),
<https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202021601149>
- [32] I.Sapaev, E.Saitov, N.Zoxidov and B.Kamanov, Matlab-model of a solar photovoltaic station integrated with a local electrical network, IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering, Volume 883, International Scientific Conference Construction Mechanics, Hydraulics and Water Resources Engineering (CONMECHYDRO – 2020) 23-25 April 2020, Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and Agricultural Mechanization Engineers, Tashkent, Uzbekistan,
<https://doi:10.1088/1757-899X/883/1/012116>
- [33] Javoxir Toshov and Elyor Saitov, Portable autonomous solar power plant for individual use, E3S Web of Conferences 139, 01087 (2019),
<https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/201913901087>
- [34] M. K. Bakhadyrkhanov, S. A. Valiev, N. F. Zikrillaev, S. V. Koveshnikov, E. B. Saitov & S. A. Tachilin, Silicon photovoltaic cells with clusters of nickel atoms, Direct Conversion of Solar Energy into Electric Energy, Published: 22 February 2017. Volume 52, pages 278–281, (2016),
<https://doi.org/10.3103/S0003701X1604006X>